

Socio Cultural factors influencing Entrepreneurial growth: A study on Small Medium Enterprises: A selected towns-south Ethiopia

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ABSTRACT

Over the years, a number of theories have been used to explain the impact of socio-cultural environment on entrepreneurial emergence. The theories tried to explain the social and cultural characteristics which cause people to be or not to be entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurship has been found to be a factor in socio-economic and human development. Its study has, however, been largely viewed from economic perspective in Ethiopia. This work was an effort to approach the problem of entrepreneurial event among Ethiopian entrepreneurs from socio-cultural perspective. The target of this study was to determine the socio-cultural factors affecting entrepreneurial growth in especially in SME sector in ArbaMinch province. 100 Entrepreneurs were selected based on simple random sampling. The measurement instrument of the research was questionnaire. The study used questionnaires, interviews and observation schedule, Descriptive and analytic procedures were employed. The current research was a correlation type. Data analysis resulted using Pearson and regression coefficient showed that socio-cultural factors had positive effect on entrepreneurial growth in SME. The paper determines that, in overall, socio-cultural environment significantly impact on entrepreneurial growth in the selected area. Outside the negative or adverse Socio-economic situations of individuals, the culture and value system of a people is a prodigious cause of the craving and capacity of people fetching entrepreneurs.

1. Introduction

Over the past years, it has become increasingly apparent that, Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) indeed contribute to employment and economic development (Wube, 2010). Entrepreneurship has always been linked to wealth generation and economic growth in the modern society (Tilley & Young, 2009). Entrepreneurship has been widely accepted as a process in which individuals discover, create and exploit business opportunities (Venkataraman, 1997). Schumpeter (1967, p.621) has pointed out that economic development depends to a large extent on the active and enthusiastic participation of intelligent entrepreneurs in the economic process. Haggan E (1961, pp.191-224) viewed economic development is seen almost exclusively as a process of technological change which is brought in by the creativity of the entrepreneurs. Studies have shown that small-scale industries in many countries provide the mechanism for promoting indigenous entrepreneurship, enhancing greater opportunities per unit of capital invested and aiding the development of local technology (Nils-Henrik and Morch, 1995). Research work on small-scale industries has shown that small-scale forest-based processing enterprises form a very large part of the overall forest products processing total in employment terms (FAO, 1995). Thus, in any country, economic developmental activities are centered on the entrepreneurship of the people of that country. The small scale industries are the hub of many economic activities in a developing country like Ethiopia.

Poverty eradication has been the major goal of small enterprise development in most developing countries. The small

and medium scale industries represent 80 percent of industrial base of most of the developed countries (Mathew, 1999, p.23).

Hoselitz (1952, pp.193-220) pointed out that some writers identified entrepreneurship with the function of uncertainty bearing, other with the co-ordination of productive resources, some others with the introduction of innovations and skills. There are various factors such as need for independence, improving financial position, self-fulfilment, desire to be own boss etc motivates an entrepreneur (SavitaBalhara & et.al, p.9). Some factors such as age, gender, and individual background such as education and former work experience have an impact on entrepreneurial intention and endeavor. Kristiansen, et al (2003, pp.251-263) found that human capital or human resource such as age, gender, education and experience is a further influence on the decision to become self-employed. Christopher's (1974, p.109) study revealed that economic gain as the most important reason for starting the small industrial units. High demand for the product perceived, was the most encouraging factor. The basic rationale of developing SMEs is that they provide additional employment opportunities and ensure more equitable distribution of income and better standard of living. Appropriate technological guidance through establishment of entrepreneurship business development could only help entrepreneurship to gain guidance and counselling to improve their economy. An entrepreneur is a person who always looking for change, responds to change, and exploits it as an opportunity. With adequate requirement of capital, education facility and own creativity, intelligence, energetic youth can be turned into a decent business people. These variables are backed by socio cultural and economic factors of a country.

2. Background of the Study

Over the years, a number of theories have been used to explain the impact of socio-cultural environment on entrepreneurial emergence. The theories tried to explain the social and cultural characteristics which cause people to be or not to be entrepreneurs. The earliest theory on the influence of socio-cultural environment on entrepreneurship was that of Max Weber, a German sociologist. In his theory, Weber explained that society plays a big role in developing entrepreneurs. This is because the individual draws his values from the social values, mores and institutional framework within which he lives (Van de Ven, 1993). Weber's theory is that the socio-cultural systems in which individuals live provide a set of values from which personal values and thinking pattern of people are based, and these in turn influence the decision by individuals positively or negatively towards entrepreneurship, i.e. whether or not to be entrepreneurs. Fundamentally, social systems and culture affect the development of entrepreneurial spirit and motivation by exhibiting values that either enhance or inhibit entrepreneurship behaviour and drive amongst people. The micro and small business sector is recognized as an integral component of economic development and a crucial element in the effort to lift countries out of poverty (Wolfenson, 2007:28-39). The dynamic role of micro and small enterprises (MSEs) in developing countries as engines through which the growth objectives of developing countries can be achieved has long been recognized. It is estimated that MSEs employ 22% of the adult population in developing countries (Fisseha, 2006:43).

Socio-cultural environment in broad terms consists of both the social system and the culture of a people. It refers primarily to man created intangible elements which affect people's behaviour, relationship, perception and way of life, and their survival and existence. In other words, the social-cultural environment consists all elements, conditions and influences which shape the personality of an individual and potentially affect his attitude, disposition, behaviour, decisions and activities. Such elements include beliefs, values, attitudes, habits, forms of behaviour and life styles of persons as developed from cultural, religious, educational and social conditioning, (Bennett and Kassarjian, 1972; Adeleke et.al, 2003).

According to Wetherly (2011) and Felicia et al. (2013), socio-cultural environment is described as an environment which consisting of everything that is not contained within the economy or political system. It is a social-cultural system which is made up of collection of activities and relationships through which people engage in their personal and private lives which include population features, age, ethnicity, religion, values, attitude, lifestyles and associates.

These environmentally relevant patterns of behaviour lead to the creation of different cultural values in different societies, some of which influence the decision to create new businesses. Therefore, culture, as distinct from political, social, technological or economic contexts, has relevance for economic behaviour and business performance (Shapero&Sokol, 1982; Shane, 1993).

2.1 Statement of the Problem

Culture shapes social and economic institutions and also a source of personality development. Worldwide integration and development has modified the traditional identifications through which intra-national cultural differences contribute to entrepreneurial behavioural differences (Linan 2009). To determine the entrepreneurial intention, it is very important to study the culture. Social values and beliefs concerning about entrepreneurship have an effect on the motivational background of intention, on the other hand skills are also important factor for entrepreneurial intention. Individuals who have entrepreneurial skills are more prone to adopt entrepreneurship than those who do not have those skills (Linan 2009).

This research will investigate how Socio cultural factors plays its role in developing entrepreneurial intentions, Education, Family commitment and expectations of family and friends influence individual for developing entrepreneurial growth. Development of new business through entrepreneurship directly impact on societies and economies grow and prosper. There has been considerable research based on psychological and economic approaches to entrepreneurship, the influence of socio-cultural factors, Religion, Ethnicity , Family, Physical attributes, Economic Status, Education, make an impact on entrepreneurial development process in developing country. Therefore, the aim of this Research is to put together all factors from a theoretical perspective, the socio-cultural factors and entrepreneurial activity. In this research an appropriate framework to develop future research analyzing the socio-cultural factors that influence the Entrepreneurial growth in selected area.

2.2 Objectives of the Study:

General objective e of this research is to assess the influence of socio-Cultural factors on entrepreneurship development of the SMEs. The key objective of the study is to identify the silent effects of socio-Cultural factors on the entrepreneurship development of the SMEs in the study area and to establish the productive prospects of progressive SMEs.

2.2.1 Specific Objectives

Identification of socio and cultural factors which encumber the development of entrepreneurial growth in Arba Minch region-Ethiopia

1. To analyse the social, and cultural factors how it is influencing the entrepreneurial growth : with the following framework - Religion, Family, Physical attributes, Economic Status, Education, Locality (Location)
2. To examine different other motivational Factors contributes the Entrepreneurial growth i.e educational background, occupational experience , assistance from financial institutions, availability of technology and other factors

1.3 Hypothesis of the study:

- H0 : There is no significant impact of socio factors is a source on developing the entrepreneurial growth
- H0: Cultural factors have no significant influence on developing the entrepreneurial growth.

- H0 : There is no significant impact on motivational factors is a source on developing entrepreneurial growth

3. Review of Literature

(Ács et al., 2008; van Praag and Versloot, 2007) The entrepreneurship literature generally takes a restricted view of development. Most empirical studies on the relationship between entrepreneurship and development have similarly been limited to GDP, productivity and employment growth as proxies for development – and not multi-dimensional development.

Entrepreneurship becomes the important tool for economic development of a country (Faltin 2001). It is the way of self-employment which is the alternative way to rout out of poverty (Bogan and Darity 2007).

(Guerrero et. al. 2008). Start-up of new business has significant impact on social and economic growth and is the source of innovation. The functions, activities and actions associated with exploiting opportunities and form an organization has become a universal trait Economic strength of a country is important for the social and cultural strength of a country. Without it certain factors do not flourish in the area for long term such as education (Pardeep and Poonam 2011).

Cultural values are the essential element to make sense about entrepreneurship which influences the behaviours of people in a society (Turker 2009). Social norms are the unrecorded rules of conduct of a group which impact the individual-level decision-making process. These are shared by others and prevail in society by their approval which maintain unwanted motivations and helps an individual in decision making process. Social norms help an individual in changing behaviour according to environment (Meek et. al. 2010).

Subjective norms have influence on entrepreneurial behaviour due to unemployment and family commitment. Expectations of family and friends influence an individual for entrepreneurial behaviour (Kennedy et. al. 2003).

Socio cultural factors have well been accepted as influential drivers for entrepreneurship (Shivani et al., 2006). A person is surrounded by cultural, social, economical and cultural factors which affects on the entrepreneurial intention and helps in enhancing self-confidence, risk-taking ability and innovation. Education has significant affect on entrepreneurial intention (Turker and Selcuk 2009).

The factors such as family background and orientation are sources for entrepreneurial characteristics and the emergence of entrepreneurs. The theory emphasized the role of the family in developing the entrepreneurial character. It is believed that the home atmosphere and values of an entrepreneurial family can provide a great deal of nurturing and support for development of entrepreneurial personality or character (Kuratko 1989).

Family as unit of socio-cultural activities provides plate form for initiating economic activity for the creation of firms and

growth. Family represents the important part of culture and has the significant impact on the firm performance (Steier 2004).

Family business has greater influence on entrepreneurial intention because family has a greater role in career choice. Family business has stronger awareness of its impacts on new generation who want to become entrepreneur. (Carr et. al. 2007)

Methodology: The study is mainly concerned in terms of drive, extent of controlling variables, and data collection done correspondingly. In this study is descriptive and exploratory research will be used. It has both qualitative and quantitative research will be used. Qualitative research will be applied to explain the nature of relationship of the phenomena and to obtain systematic sequence of information to get into the depth of research problem. On the other hand, Quantitative research will be used to provide numerical measurement and analysis of the magnitude and extent of the problem. Quantitative research use statistical analysis to obtain findings which are express numerically (Geoffey 2005). Concerning sources of data, both primary and secondary sources will be used in generating valuable and relevant data. Primary source: primary data will be collected through field work survey, interview, questionnaire, and focus group discussions. Secondary data will be collected from officially published and unpublished materials. Reports, statistical bulletins, brochures and other material have been used for other necessary information.

Data were collected in two stages and designed by a questionnaire. First, research questionnaire were distributed among 30 business units to assess socio cultural factors to test its validity. Next, after removing some problems of the questionnaire, the original questionnaire containing 30 questions distributed among entrepreneurs in Arba Minch rural and urban area, the respondents to provide correct answers. 5-choice Likert scaling gives respondents a set of statements that they asked i.e 1=Strongly Disagree to 5=strongly agree. was also used. Reliability of the questionnaire and its aspects was calculated as follows using spss software.

Table 1: Reliability of questionnaire components

Name of the factor	Cronbach's alpha value
Social factors	0.78
Cultural factors	0.81
Other motivational factors	0.76
All components	0.71

Research Findings: The Examination of research variables indicates that characteristics of the individual (age, education, entrepreneurship, education level of business people, and years of experience) is also true for selected entrepreneur of this study. For the research Statistical distribution were done and investigated demographic variables is existing in Table 2. Most respondents were between 30 and 40. These results are similar to the obtained results of the research review of literature examined the status of entrepreneur in other countries. Most SME entrepreneur in were between 30-40 with a High school or college education.

Age	Frequency	Percentage
21-30	16	23.53
31-40	43	63.24
40-50	6	8.82
50-60	3	4.41
Level of Education		
Primary	13	19.12
High school	37	54.41
Colleges	18	26.47
No of employees		
Less than 5	35	51.47
5-10	20	29.41
10-15	10	14.70
15-20	3	4.41
Years of experience		
Below one year	22	32.35
1-4	25	36.76
5-8	13	19.11
8-10	8	11.76

As a part of demographic information the researcher requested the respondents to indicate their gender so as to see their distribution as out of 68 respondents 70 % of the respondents were male and 30% of the respondents were female so it is influences that there is a small degree of gender difference among the entrepreneur. In terms of age The majority of the respondents between 31-40 with 63.24 percentage and the findings disclosed that most of them are below 40 years and most of the employees had worked for long periods of time and it will be given the required experience to understand the dynamics of socio cultural factors on entrepreneurial growth .

In next stage, weighted mean was computed and scores placed with the their ranges of the continuous Likert scale. The scores of both very low and small extent represented variables of 0 to 2.5 as mean on the scale . on the scale moderate extent was represented by a figure of 2.5 to 3.4 as mean . great extent and very great extent were represented by figures to 3.5 to 5.0 as mean . Standard deviation of >.9 implies significant difference on the impact of the variable among respondents.

	Factor	Mean	Std Deviation
Social factors	Social status	4.0147	.88536
	Social dignity	3.8911	.87292
	Community relations	4.0121	.86272
	Social dependency	3.8812	.87746
	Social changes	3.7541	.82131
	Previous Experience	2.9211	.86654
	Peer group influence	2.7821	.77536

	Factor	Mean	Std Deviation
Cultural factors	Cultural values	3.7921	.89335
	Beliefs of people	3.8675	.92138
	Traditions and local influences	2.7685	.72719
	Religious influence	3.9706	.95719
	Local and regional language	3.6256	.81275
	Laws and rules	3.2753	.71751

	Factor	Mean	Std Deviation
Other motivational factors	Personality factor	3.7149	.82015
	Psychological factors	4.8283	1.8154
	Economic policy	3.7609	.85461
	Social dependency	3.8971	.99461
	Assistance from the financial institutions	4.6462	1.9684
	Availability of technology and factors	3.7946	.91652

Mean score and standard deviation are the most frequently used in descriptive research study .the researcher employed mean score interpretation to support the inferential static result by rating the socio cultural factors effecting the entrepreneurial growth. Accordingly the mean interpretation in this study was conducted from the respondents by mean score on likert scale that the range was strongly disagree(1)to strongly agree (5), accordingly the scores of strongly disagree and disagree (Low commitment) have taken to respect a variable which had a mean score of (0 to 2.5). the scores of moderate agree(medium commitment)have been taken to respect a variable with a mean score of 2.5 to 3.4 and the score of both agree and strongly agree(high commitment) have been taken to represent a variable which had a mean score of 3.5 to 5 and also a standard deviation of >0.9 implies a significant difference on the impact of the variable among respondents.

In this study the summary of the descriptive statistics is shown in the above table all variables were conducted based on a 5 point likert scale. Accordingly, the results shows that the mean mean for social status was (4.0147) with a S.D(0.88526) which indicates that the respondents felt that their social status is high to words the entrepreneurial growth . and also the mean score shown in the table infer that the peer group experience from the social factors towards the growth of the entrepreneurship. Hence the peer group influence to words the entrepreneurial growth is low which may lose the potential entrepreneurs since the mean score is 2.7821 . and also the previous experience which doesn't have that much influence in the support and growth of entrepreneurship where the mean score form the socio factors is(2.9211)

And the cultural factors were also investigated in the study the respondents view regarding the cultural factors cultural values was Mean of 3.7921 and sd is .89335and the other Beliefs of people mean score is 3.8675 and sd is .92138 Traditions and local influences towards the influence on entrepreneurial growth is Mean 2.7685 and sd is .72719, and the Religious influence in entrepreneurship is moderate in terms of Mean score is 3.9706 and sd is .95719. Local and

regional language influence in entrepreneurial growth is moderate agree and the Mean score is 3.6256 and Sd is .81275 and thus the mean score variables of the above variables were moderate.

Some of the other motivational factors which is going to influence the entrepreneur growth Personality factor mean score is 3.7149 and the Sd is .82015 Assistance from the financial institutions mean score is 4.6462 and sd is 1.9684 and the other motivational factors are influencing in entrepreneurial growth is High.

Table 3: Findings of the research hypotheses

Hypothesis	Independent variable	Correlation	The significance level
The first hypothesis	Social factors	0.801	0.742
The second hypothesis	Cultural factors	0.940	0.825
The third hypothesis	Motivational factors	0.423	0.738

First hypothesis: economic factors have no effect on women's entrepreneurship

Table 3 indicates that significance level is greater than 0.5 Therefore, the null hypothesis is not confirmed at confidence level of 95%. In other words, there is a correlation between social factors and dependent variable of entrepreneurship growth.

Second hypothesis: cultural factors have a significant effect on entrepreneurship growth

The table also shows that significance level is greater than 0.5. Therefore, the null hypothesis is confirmed at confidence level of 95%. In other words, there is a correlation between cultural factors and dependent variable of entrepreneurial growth.

The third hypothesis: motivational factors have a significant effect on entrepreneurship growth.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

The analyses discovered primarily that socio-cultural factors can influence both positively and negatively entrepreneurial emergence in a society. The references in the analysis confirm opinions in the theories of entrepreneurial emergence which are

rooted in the theory of social behavior. It also focuses on values and occurrences that the behavior and the individual decision process is being influenced and motivated by socio cultural aspects. The lifestyles including social and economic conditions are also influenced as indicated in the study. An individual person with his distinct characteristics influences the society as well. The socio cultural environment has all its dynamics to influence the environment as well as individual values which directly influence his decisions and actions in all endeavours. Entrepreneurship helps to generate wealth and form capital in the country which ultimately contributes to the economic growth of the country. It filled the life of countryman with prosperity, and it helps to fight against poverty, unemployment and generate opportunities for the people. This study focuses on the social-cultural impact on the Entrepreneurship Social status, relationship between other members, social dignity, directly and indirectly, help the entrepreneur to be a risk taker and implement new thoughts and ideas. The family does affect the person to select the entrepreneurship as a career. Their moral and financial support means a lot to the budding entrepreneurs. Friends and peers are also one source for a person to be an entrepreneur. Their skill knowledge, training, and contacts help him to grow as an entrepreneur. Compare to individualistic culture, collective culture impact more on the entrepreneur to succeed in the venture.

1. In this study, economic, social and cultural factors effect were investigated. It is suggested that each of the factors to be considered in more detail.
2. It is suggested to study performance of the government institutions in promoting a culture of entrepreneurship and entrepreneurial development in future studies.

Finally, according to increasing participation of women in social activities, we hope to see authorities support of entrepreneurship, development of entrepreneurial culture and elimination of social and economic barriers to reduce unemployment .

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